

Verbal constructional profiles: reliability, distinction power and practical applications

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Abstract

In this paper we explore the notion of constructional profiles (the frequency distribution of a given linguistic item across syntactic environments) from two angles, methodological and applied. We concentrate on verbal constructional profiles, using Russian argument frame data in two different dependency formats. We first test the profiles' stability and distinction power across sample sizes, and then use the profiles in two tasks concerning Russian aspect: to identify the aspectual partner of a given verb and to guess whether a given verb is perfective or imperfective.

1 Introduction

A linguistic profile is a frequency distribution of occurrences of a linguistic item across a given parameter. Because it contains useful quantitative information about an item's usage, such profiles can help us discover fundamental properties of the item [3]. Here we focus on verbal constructional profiles, where the item is always a verb, and the parameter is its syntactic environment. This methodology has been used for various purposes with some success [2, 4, 7], but little is known about the basic properties of the profiles.

We start by addressing two general methodological questions in section 4. First, is there such thing as a reliable constructional profile, i.e. is there a stable distribution that we might want to approximate? If yes, what corpus size is required to capture it? Second, what distinction power do the profiles possess at different corpus sizes? To test that, we used the SynTagRus treebank of modern Russian [1, 11], both in its native dependency format and converted into the PROIEL format (see section 3). As a secondary goal, we compare the two dependency schemes' ability to yield useful argument structure data.

We then zoom in on a more language-specific question and estimate the possibility of using verbal constructional profiles as an objective criterion in the study of Russian aspect, with a view to use it in diachronic studies, in particular, to apply it to Old Russian where the aspectual properties of verbs are often highly unclear. In section 5 we test the method's applicability to modern Russian aspect, taking

into account our methodological results. We test two different hypotheses: first, that constructional profiles can be used to identify the most likely aspectual partner of a verb; second, that constructional profiles can be used to tell whether a verb is perfective or imperfective. We see that both hypotheses hold to some extent, but only the second one yields results that are good enough to be of practical use for our purposes.¹

2 Constructional profiles

The constructional profile of a given verb is a set of pairs {argument frame; frequency}, where the argument frame is a set of dependents that are considered arguments (as opposed to adjuncts).² By frequency we mean the relative frequency of occurrence of the frame with a given verb. Two small example profiles in the two formats (see more about the formats in section 3) are seen in table 1.

verb	PROIEL				SynTagRus			
	frame	abs. freq.	rel. freq.		frame	abs. freq.	rel. freq.	
<i>vysypat'</i>	V+obj	1	0.20	V+1-kompl	1	0.20		
	V+sub+obl	2	0.40	V+predik+sravnit	1	0.20		
	V+sub+obj+obl	1	0.20	V+1-kompl+2-kompl+predik	1	0.20		
	V+obj+obl	1	0.20	V+2-kompl+predik	1	0.20		
<i>vylivat'</i>	V+obj+obl	1	0.33	V+1-kompl+3-kompl	1	0.33		
	V+sub+obj	2	0.67	V+1-kompl+predik	2	0.67		

Table 1: Simple constructional profiles for the verbs *vysypat'* ‘pour out (solids)’ and *vylivat'* ‘pour out (liquids)’

One of the most important things one can do with profiles is to compare them. The similarity of two profiles can be measured as their intersection rate (adapted from [7]), which is calculated as follows. For every frame that occurs in both compared profiles, we look at its relative frequencies in both profiles, take the smallest of these two values and add up all such values. If we compare the profiles of *vysypat'* ‘pour out (solids)’ and *vylivat'* ‘pour out (liquids)’, we will get an intersection rate of 0.2 regardless of which annotation scheme we use (see 1). Only one frame (V+obj+obl in PROIEL, V+1-kompl+3-kompl in SynTagRus) occurs in both profiles, and the smallest of its relative frequencies is 0.2.

We tried three different ways of building profiles. Table 1 illustrates the first profile type (simple), where only syntactic relation labels are included. The second

¹All raw data for this article, results and their statistical significance, and code used to perform experiments can be found at the TROLLing Dataverse, hdl:10037.1/10142.

²Verb dependents deemed to be arguments here: direct and indirect/oblique objects (including sources and goals with motion verbs), subjects, passive agents, complement clauses and various types of predicative complements.

type (partly enriched) includes basic morphological information about the verb: whether it is passive and whether it is a participle used in attributive function. The third profile type (fully enriched) additionally uses simplified morphological and lexical information about the arguments: argument infinitives are labeled as such (inf), prepositional arguments are labeled “PP”, arguments headed by subjunctions are labeled with the subjunction lemma, and nominal arguments are labeled with their case. Thus, a simple V+obl frame may for instance turn out to be a Vreflpas_attrib+obl_PP in the fully enriched profile type. Naturally, the two enriched profile types, and especially the fully enriched type, are more granular than the simple type.

3 The two formats

To address the questions outlined in section 1, we turned to SynTagRus, a large treebank of Russian (860,720 words).³ Since our goal is ultimately to study Russian aspect diachronically, we wanted to have the data in the same format that our Old Russian data are in,⁴ effectively creating a treebank spanning over a thousand years. We therefore automatically converted the whole SynTagRus into the PROIEL format, an enriched dependency grammar scheme which is used for an expanding family of treebanks of ancient languages originating in the PROIEL parallel treebank.⁵ For the experiments, we used both versions of SynTagRus: the original and the converted one.⁶

Both PROIEL and SynTagRus are dependency schemes, essentially describing the functional relationships between heads and dependents. However, both give considerably more granular argument structure representations than most dependency schemes, e.g. the Prague Dependency Treebank [10], but in very different ways. The two schemes are therefore particularly interesting to compare. The SynTagRus format, based on the Meaning–Text model [9], is the more traditional of the two schemes, in that it only allows primary dependencies and only to a limited extent allows empty nodes. The argument representation is highly granular, but without including much information on the syntactic category of the argument itself. Instead, it heavily relies on lexico-semantic properties of words. For instance, while the 1-kompl (‘first complement’) relation is typically used for direct objects, with the verb ‘to live’ it is used for PPs and adverbs denoting locations (‘to live in Norway’, ‘to live here’ etc.). The relative rank of an argument in a valency frame, not its form, decides what relation label it gets.

³Created by the Laboratory of Computational Linguistics at the Institute for Information Transmission Problems, and hosted by the Russian National Corpus (<http://ruscorpora.ru/>).

⁴The Tromsø Old Russian and OCS Treebank (TOROT) at <https://nestor.uit.no>.

⁵Found at foni.uio.no:3000 and built by members of the project *Pragmatic Resources in Old Indo-European Languages*.

⁶A conversion from the PROIEL format to the SynTagRus format is likely to be much less successful, due to the focus on lexical semantics in the latter scheme and its higher granularity. Such a conversion would have to rely heavily on lexical lists.

The PROIEL scheme is inspired by and convertible to LFG F-structures [5, 6]. Structure sharing is indicated by way of secondary dependencies (e.g. in control and raising structures, but also to indicate shared arguments and predicate identity). The format also systematically uses empty verb and conjunction nodes to account for ellipsis, gapping and asyndetic coordination. Both these features enhance argument structure representation, since less structural information is lost than in the SynTagRus scheme. Argument representation is less granular than in SynTagRus: transitive objects (obj) are distinguished from oblique objects (obl), and complement clauses (comp) and arguments with external subjects (xobj, e.g. control infinitives) have separate labels. Both schemes use a wide definition of the term “argument” – for instance, both schemes take sources and goals with motion verbs and locations with positional verbs as arguments – but the PROIEL scheme is somewhat more restrictive, which will necessarily cause differences in the constructional profiles.

The main issues encountered in the conversion process had to do with coordination and null verb insertion, since the necessary information was not always recoverable in the SynTagRus data. We were able to insert secondary dependencies to external subjects very successfully using morphological cues, but were unable to insert secondary dependencies to shared arguments. Apart from that, argument structure dependencies and labels were generally converted very successfully using lexical, morphological and part-of-speech cues. A spot check of 50 random sentences (759 words, including empty tokens) shows that the conversion was 98% accurate if only the errors relevant to argument structure were counted, whereas the overall accuracy was 90%. The two most frequent error types include wrong relation labels and wrong structure (e.g. incorrect head node), next come wrong part of speech, the least frequent type are wrong morphological features (which usually follow from a part-of-speech misclassification).

4 Profile stability and distinction power

As mentioned above, one crucial question is how reliable the constructional profiles are, or, to put it in more practical terms, what sample size is required for a profile to become stable. Profile sample size is understood here as the number of verb tokens that were used to build a profile. The profiles in table 1, for instance, have extremely small sample sizes (5 and 3), and thus are hardly reliable.

In order to estimate the relationship between profile stability and sample size, we carried out the following experiment. For a given sample size n (from 10 to 500 with step 10), all verbs that had a frequency no lower than $2n$ were found in the corpus. For every verb, two non-intersecting but otherwise random samples of the size n were drawn, a profile was built using each of these samples, and the intersection rate between the two profiles was calculated. Average values for each sample size (see more below) are presented in figure 1.⁷ The higher the intersection

⁷The fact that large sample sizes yield small sets of verbs (v) to be tested ($v = 991$ for $n = 10$,

Figure 1: Profile stability across sample sizes.

rate, the closer the two profiles built using independent samples are (ideally, we want them to be identical), and the higher the profile stability is.

As can be seen from figure 1, the simple (purely syntactic) profiles exhibit higher stability when compared to the partly enriched ones of the same sample size, while these, in turn, are more stable than fully enriched ones. This is unsurprising, since as profiles include more information (in this case about morphology), they become more granular, and require larger samples to become stable. For the same reason, the PROIEL format gives slightly higher stability than the SynTagRus format for the profiles of the same type. In general, the differences between simple, partly enriched and fully enriched profiles are more salient than those between the SynTagRus and PROIEL schemes.

Stability per se, however, tells us very little about how useful the profiles can be, how much information they contain. To estimate that, we measure another parameter, the distinction power, or how unique each profile is, how well it can identify its verb. To do that, we performed a similar procedure, going through different sample sizes, drawing two non-intersecting, but otherwise random samples for each verb and using them to build two profiles. One of these profiles was included into a control set, one into a test set. We then tried to use the profiles to match verbs. For every profile from the test set, the intersection rate was calculated between it and every profile from the control set, and the control profile which exhibits the largest intersection rate was considered a match. Afterwards, we checked whether the matched profiles actually belonged to the same verb (success) or not

$v = 5$ for $n = 500$) is accounted for by bootstrapping: the procedure of drawing two random samples for each verb was repeated m times, where m is a minimal possible number that satisfies the condition $v * m \geq 1000$ (for instance, $m = 2$ for $n = 10$, $m = 200$ for $n = 500$) The total number of datapoints is thus never less than 1000.

(failure). To increase robustness, the procedure was repeated 30 times, drawing different samples each time. The average results for selected sample sizes are provided in table 2. Note that sample size here refers to the sample size of profiles, i.e. the number of examples used to build every profile. Since we are interested in how the profile sample size influences its distinction power, or its uniqueness, we need to compare the success rates across sample sizes. For that purpose we fix the number of verbs being matched at 27 (the number of verbs available at the largest analyzed sample size), otherwise the success rate would depend not only on the profiles’ properties, but also on the number of verbs in the test set. The baseline is thus always 0.037 (=1/27, the random level).

sample size	SynTagRus			PROIEL		
	simple	partly enriched	fully enriched	simple	partly enriched	fully enriched
5	0.258	0.301	0.423	0.252	0.312	0.386
55	0.759	0.843	0.937	0.798	0.829	0.922
105	0.828	0.854	0.959	0.853	0.886	0.940
155	0.950	0.964	0.992	0.949	0.966	0.990
205	0.949	0.985	0.996	0.983	0.996	0.999

Table 2: Average success rate at the matching task across profile sample sizes.

For both schemes and all profile types, the differences between the achieved success rate and the baseline (the performance of a random guesser) are highly significant at every sample size, and effect sizes are immense. Note that even at a sample size as small as 5, the profiles are of some use, at 55 results are very good, and after 105 they start approaching the ceiling. Importantly, the more enriched the profiles are, the higher distinction power they possess. Unlike with the stability parameter, here increased granularity does the profile good service, allowing it to “recognize” the verb better.

We see that PROIEL does slightly better than SynTagRus with simple and partly enriched profiles, despite the fact that its profiles are less granular. This is probably due to the fact that the PROIEL relations are better correlated with the morphosyntactic properties of the argument, and this policy serves the given purpose better than SynTagRus lexically-based annotation. With fully enriched profiles, when information about argument morphology is available, SynTagRus slightly outperforms PROIEL.

Both types of differences are more salient for small sample sizes, with large samples, the performance is always almost at the ceiling level.

5 Russian aspect

Modern Russian has a system where aspect is expressed lexically through opposing pairs (*pisat'*, *na-pisat'* resp. ‘write.imperfective’ and ‘write.perfective’). Traditionally, context substitution tests are used as criteria to establish such partnerships,

and also to tell whether a verb is perfective or imperfective. However, these tests rely on native speaker intuitions, and cannot be applied to historical data. Also, the native speakers are not always sure about partnerships even in the modern system [7, 102–106]. We therefore try to apply constructional profiles to these two tasks. To find out if we can use them as an objective criterion in the study of Russian aspect, we need to know what the profiles measure. We suggest two possibilities.

The first possibility is that constructional profiles may serve as a measure of synonymy, as attempted for nouns in [4]. We expect Russian aspectual partners to be near-perfect synonyms, ideally distinguished only by aspectual properties. If we can use the constructional profiles as a measure of close synonymy, we should be able to identify a verb’s aspectual partner by the two verbs’ intersection rate, as [7] suggests.

The second possibility is that the constructional profiles of aspectual partners may serve as a measure of dissimilarity between aspectual partners rather than of similarity. First, it may be the case that verbal constructional profile data will not group the best synonyms together, but rather cluster verbs into syntactically relevant verb classes, perhaps similar to Levin classes [8]. Clustering experiments using argument frame data similar to ours (see e.g. [12] and [13]) suggest that this may be so. Second, it may be that aspectual partners differ systematically with respect to argument realisation. We know that perfective and imperfective verbs have at least somewhat different preferences, mostly due to the perfective verbs’ affinity for specific arguments and the imperfective verbs’ affinity for non-specific or generic arguments. If this is the case, then constructional profiles may serve as a basis for guessing the aspect of a given verb.

5.1 Aspectual partners

In order to test whether constructional profiles can serve as an objective criterion for establishing aspectual partners, we select all verbs that, according to the Syn-TagRus annotation, have a partner. From this subset of paired verbs we select those where both partners have a frequency higher than a given cutoff. From these verbs, two are considered to be partners iff, first, one is imperfective and one is perfective (“homoaspectual marriages” are forbidden), second, the perfective partner’s profile has the highest intersection rate with the imperfective partner’s profile among all perfective verbs, third, the imperfective partner’s profile has the highest intersection rate with the perfective partner’s profile among all imperfective verbs. In other words, “polygamy” is forbidden, too: one verb can have either one partner or no partners (if the guesser fails to find a partner that fulfills the criteria above). We use the fully enriched profiles since they are the most informative, and run the experiment for both annotation schemes. The results for different cutoffs are provided in table 3. Note that the first column shows the frequency cutoff, not the actual profile sample size. Sample sizes are different for every verb, since the guesser tries to use all available information, i.e. all the examples with the given verb.

While the results for high sample sizes (and smaller verb sets to choose a part-

frequency cutoff	SynTagRus	PROIEL	number of pairs
10	0.21	0.17	992
60	0.67	0.55	164
110	0.80	0.71	90
160	0.78	0.81	54
210	0.80	0.87	30
260	1.00	1.00	20
310	1.00	1.00	14

Table 3: Success rates (share of pairs correctly identified) of aspect partner matching

ner from) look quite impressive, it is important to remember that the guesser has been given a lot of useful information: first, it knows that every verb in the test set should have a partner; second, it knows which verbs are perfective and which are imperfective. If this information is removed, the performance decreases significantly. While the results are theoretically interesting (constructional profiles do allow us to find partners under certain conditions), we do not currently see any possibility to put them to practical use. If we, for instance, are faced with Old Russian data, where samples are not going to be large (but verbs are numerous), and it is not known with certainty which aspect a given verb belongs to, and whether it has a partner, the guesser, at least in its current simple form, will not be of much help.

At this task, the SynTagRus native annotation scheme outperforms PROIEL for smaller cutoffs, but loses out at higher ones.

5.2 Identifying aspect

In the second task, we try to identify the aspect of a given verb. We perform the experiment on our modern Russian data, but with a view to apply similar methods to Old Russian data. While for modern Russian it is almost always instantly obvious to a native speaker whether a verb is perfective or imperfective, that is not true for Old Russian, and intuition can easily lead to errors.

First, we create two average aspectual profiles. The imperfective profile contains frames from profiles of all imperfective verbs and arithmetic means of their relative frequencies in every profile. The perfective profile is created by the same method applied to perfective verbs. Verbs with frequencies lower than 10 are not included in the average profiles.

We then perform the comparison task: for every verb with a frequency higher than a given cutoff a constructional profile is created, and the profile is compared with both the average perfective and the average imperfective profile. Importantly, the profile of the verb being tested gets excluded from the respective average profile (since we pretend that we do not know the aspect of this verb, we should not be able to decide whether its profile should be included into perfective or imperfective average profile; in other words, the guesser does not know anything about the verb).

The guesser then chooses the aspect depending on which average profile has the higher intersection rate with the verb profile.

The results can be seen in table 4. We report only the best results, which can be achieved using the partly enriched profiles in the PROIEL format. Fully enriched PROIEL profiles give almost the same results, but do marginally worse at some sample sizes. The same is true for fully enriched SynTagRus profiles, while the discrepancies are bigger. Partly enriched SynTagRus profiles do noticeably worse. It is not quite clear what the reason for these effects is, but the most plausible hypothesis would be that the SynTagRus scheme and the full morphological information make the profiles too granular for the given task (which, as we have shown, decreases their reliability), while the partly enriched PROIEL-format profiles turn out to be “just right”.

frequency cutoff	success rate	number of verbs
10	0.71	1710
60	0.75	375
110	0.76	197
160	0.78	120
210	0.74	80
260	0.71	65
310	0.72	50
360	0.76	33
410	0.78	27
460	0.78	18

Table 4: Success rate of the aspect identification task

The differences between our guesser and the baseline (random choice of aspect) are significant at the 0.05 level (two-sided proportions test with Yates’ continuity correction) for cutoffs smaller than 210.⁸ Higher cutoffs, as can be seen from the table, result in smaller samples, and the significance testing lacks power. For our purposes, however, the smaller sample sizes are the most interesting, and the performance is never lower than 70% here. Given that a more sophisticated guesser can potentially be devised, these results give some hope about constructional profiles serving as an independent diagnostic for determining the aspect of a given verb.

6 Conclusions

In this paper we explored the notion of verbal constructional profiles from two main angles using Russian data on two dependency grammar formats.

⁸It can be argued that the baseline should be represented not by a random guesser, but by one which always chooses the answer “imperfective”, since imperfective verbs are more numerous than perfective at any cutoff. However, an adequate measure of performance would then be not accuracy, but F-score (with perfectives being a positive class). While F-scores for our guesser will be lower than plain accuracy, for the “always-imperfective” guesser they will always be 0.

Our first angle was chiefly methodological. In section 4 we established that the existence of a “true” distribution can be claimed. Learning curves like Figure 1 can be used to determine what sample size is required to get a stable profile and claim a reasonable approximation to the “true” distribution. We refrain here from providing any specific thresholds, since the numbers, as has been shown, depend on the profile type and annotation scheme and, probably, also on the language in question. We can, however, note that for small samples (10–20 examples) stability is low. This is important to know, since in some cases researchers are forced to rely on small samples. One example would be studies on infrequent verbs (and, as is well-known, the majority of words are infrequent), another one – studies based on relatively small treebanks (e.g. of exotic or ancient languages). As expected, less granular profiles become stable at smaller sample sizes than more granular profiles, so at this task simple PROIEL profiles performed best.

When we looked at the distinction power of the constructional profiles, however, granularity proved to be an advantage, and the most granular profiles (SynTagRus fully enriched profiles) performed best. Even very small samples allow us to identify some verbs, and decent-size samples do very well. Enriched profiles, being more granular, require larger sample sizes, but for the same reason have higher distinction power than simple profiles. Interestingly, unless fully enriched profiles are used, the less granular PROIEL scheme outperforms the more granular SynTagRus scheme at the matching test nonetheless, probably due to the former scheme’s sensitivity to the morphosyntactic category of the argument. With fully enriched profiles, however, the PROIEL scheme loses its advantage, and the more granular SynTagRus shows slightly better results.

In general, we saw that both schemes provided good argument frame data, but that the PROIEL scheme’s small set of syntactic relation labels were more informative than the larger set of SynTagRus valency labels when using frames unenriched with argument morphology.

In section 5 we turned to practical applications. We found that verbal constructional profiles may be used both to guess aspectual partners and to establish the aspect of a given verb. Granularity was also an important parameter in these tasks: aspect partner matching works best with fully enriched SynTagRus profiles, whereas aspect identification worked best with partly enriched PROIEL profiles. While the aspect partner matching task was mostly interesting from a theoretical point of view (the method is not applicable for low- and medium-frequency verbs), the aspect identification task gave more hopeful results. Even at very low frequency cutoffs, we had good results with determining aspect. This is a measure that may potentially serve as an independent criterion to decide the aspectuality of verbs in diachronic studies.

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